

Viewpoint

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Meeting the challenges posed by mass-produced manuscripts and click-data science

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Abstract

The combination of open-access datasets, machine learning workflows, increased computing capacity, and generative artificial intelligence has effectively removed many of the rate-limiting steps in manuscript production. This has created an industry of click-data science and a flood of low-quality manuscripts based on large health datasets such as the US National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, the UK Biobank, and the US FDA Adverse Event Reporting System. These papers often employ statistically appropriate methods and real data, but introduce misleading results and false discoveries to the literature. Here, we offer suggestions for editors on how to identify such manuscripts and reject them at the point of submission, reducing the burden on the publishing process.

Keywords:

big data, false discoveries, generative AI, integrity, paper mills

Fraudulent and low quality research is exploiting Open Science data sources

Until recently, 'big data' driven research has been hampered by a number of rate-limiting steps, including the acquisition of high-quality data, the application of complex methods, and the production of publication-ready manuscripts. The combination of easily accessible large datasets (motivated by Open Science principles),¹ robust coding libraries in languages such as R and Python, and generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) has effectively removed these rate-limiting steps from the authoring process. This represents a huge productivity gain for researchers in the form of click-data science, that is, low-effort manuscript production powered by open data and automation. The benefits, however, have accrued not only to those that wish to proceed cautiously and ethically, but also to those whose agenda is publication at all costs. The latter category includes paper mills—commercial organisations that produce manuscripts for paying clients at scale using derivative, copied, and/or fabricated text or data sets.²⁻⁵

Examples of large (often national) datasets include the US National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) or the UK Biobank.^{6,7} These provide wide-ranging and complex information on genomes, epidemiology or medication and provide the data on an open access basis. This often includes Application Programming Interfaces that allow data to be extracted directly into a coding environment for rapid analysis. Combined with GenAI's ability to author introductory or discussion text, this allows for end-to-end automated workflows for manuscript production. The consequences are

clearly visible in increased submission volumes and publication rates. A simple search of the PubMed database for "NHANES [tiab]" shows a four-fold increase from 1081 accepted publications in 2021 to 4060 in 2024, with further growth probable in 2025 based on the year-to-date trend. There has also been a shift towards formulaic titles reporting an association between exposure X and outcome Y for cohort Z.⁸

Similar growth has been reported for papers that use Mendelian randomisation applied to open genome-wide association study datasets,⁹ such as FinnGen.¹⁰ Another area experiencing formulaic growth is pharmacovigilance, especially exploiting the US FDA Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS).¹¹ Often these manuscripts are simplistic: at best, they offer little insight into complex multifactorial problems, and at worst, introduce false discoveries and misleading conclusions to the literature.^{12,13} Figure 1 illustrates the acceleration in aggregated publication rates across NHANES, FAERS, the Global Burden of Disease Study, FinnGen, and the UK Biobank, but any open dataset can be exploited in this way.

The challenges posed by click-data science

The relationship between journal editors and paper mills or other unethical authors is – at its core – adversarial; adaptation is a natural outcome of such a relationship. These new, heavily automated and GenAI-assisted workflows pose different challenges from those set by manuscripts that include, for example, fraudulent Western blot images or outright p-hacking. First, for this new category of unethical submission, the

Figure 1. Artificial intelligence–assisted workflows enable rapid acceleration in publications. (A) Illustrative workflow schematic. (B) PubMed search using the following search string: “nhanes[tiab] OR uk biobank[tiab] OR finngen[tiab] OR global burden of disease study[tiab] OR faers[tiab].” The estimate for the publication count in the remainder of 2025 is derived by applying the same ratio of H2 2024 / H1 2024 publication count to the H1 2025 publication count and assumes a similar seasonal pattern of higher publication rates in the first 6 months of the year.

underlying data are not faked but are high quality, often with large numbers of participants and hence statistically well-powered cohorts. Secondly, the methods employed are sophisticated, including machine learning analyses or approaches such as Mendelian randomisation. Indeed, in the case of NHANES, we believe that mass-produced manuscripts have been in production for around 3 years and consequently have received 3 years’ worth of editor and peer reviewer feedback to iron out flaws in methodologies. Thirdly, these manuscripts often target areas of public interest such as obesity or cancer (these subjects also constitute those for which national data are most likely to be collected).

The combination of these adaptive changes by paper mills has led to manuscripts that, at least superficially, appear to address genuine issues using legitimate data and high-quality methods, with the flaws (such as selective data usage) hidden except to those willing to reproduce the studies from scratch. For editors and peer reviewers alike, this makes immediate rejection of such low-value papers more challenging. Regardless of how the publishing industry arrived at this point, the process of producing data-driven research is quickly becoming trivial. In such an environment, the question of *how* research has been conducted will decline in relative importance, and *why* the research

has been conducted will have to take on greater significance.

Practical responses to the flood of low-quality research

We have observed that each exploited dataset tends to come with its own template or formula and its own set of issues. Those concerned with genome-wide association study (GWAS) data use Mendelian randomisation and will frequently apply complex methods to derive implausible results. Examples of proposed causal relationships with no biological underpinning include semi-skimmed milk consumption protecting against depression or educational attainment increasing the risks of post-operative hernias.^{14,15} Stender et al. recommend the rejection of such papers without additional supporting evidence and have provided a template for desk rejections.⁹ Those paper mills using large-scale epidemiological data such as NHANES or the Global Burden of Disease study¹⁶ will interrogate a matrix of exposures versus outcomes and select all those that meet statistical significance (without taking account of multiple hypothesis correction that is essential when querying large datasets).^{17,18} These studies will often associate a general indicator, such as inflammation, with dozens of outcomes, reporting each as a separate manuscript. Duplicate submissions are also commonplace with slight adjustments to the cohort. For example, five essentially identical studies have been published associating infertility with the body roundness index,¹⁹ taking different subsets of the NHANES dataset each time (such as married women only, or altering the years in which the women were recruited). In our experience,

such submissions can often be immediately rejected for lack of novelty by the simple means of a literature check. More generally, as previously noted, we believe that there will need to be more emphasis in submissions on the *why* of research, rather than the *how*, given that with GenAI-assisted workflows, production of a data-driven manuscript has been reduced to a handful of clicks.

Many journals and editors are aware of these problems, and resources are available that highlight how to spot and handle potential integrity issues with manuscripts, including from the Committee on Publication Ethics²⁰ and from the Collection of Open Science Integrity Guides.²¹ Domain-specific guidelines also exist; for example the Reporting of a Disproportionality Analysis for Drug Safety Signal Detection Using Individual Case Safety Reports in Pharmacovigilance (READUS-PV) checklist, originally introduced by *Drug Safety*,²² partly intended to stem the flow of low-quality pharmacovigilance papers. Albeit, as yet this has not been effective in reducing the overall rate of FAERS publications, as submissions have simply been diverted to other journals. *The Journal of Global Health* recently published a policy paper specifically on the mass manufacture of manuscripts using click-data science workflows, including a set of Guidelines for Reporting Analyses of Big Data Repositories Open to the Public (GRABDROP).²³ This tool requires authors (a) to formally disclose their previous data repository-based publications, (b) to explain the elements of study design and how the use of available datasets makes the study an original scientific contribution, (c) to list and cite all publications addressing similar research questions from the same dataset, (d) to explain how multiple hypothesis testing

was addressed, and (e) declare whether and how GenAI chatbots had been used in the development of the manuscript.

In our view, the GRABDROP guidelines offer a helpful template for editors. Some of the points, such as the disclosure of GenAI use for writing, will already be covered by most journals' policies. Others, such as the requirement to cite previous studies using the dataset, should be standard practice anyway, but requiring a checklist has the advantage of increasing the burden for exploitative, high-volume authors at little expense to authors making genuine scientific contributions. This is an important aspect given that submission handling can already be an onerous process for editors and authors.²⁴ Inevitably, the adversarial nature of paper mills means that we expect the 'next generation' to follow GRABDROP or similar guidelines superficially to avoid detection. Where responses to checklists have obviously been falsified or misrepresented, however, there will be quick and easy grounds for desk rejection.

Preservation of data as a public good

While in the short run, click-data science can be addressed by editors and peer reviewers through increased vigilance, the target-setting culture in academia makes it likely that paper mills will continue to innovate and adapt to meet customer demand. We believe that in the longer run, these trends will also raise issues around Open Science itself. There are other models of data availability than simple unfettered access, for example through pre-registration of research or requiring applications for access that state researchers' specific areas of interest to prevent data dredging.

Such steps would still meet the goals of Open Science and are largely in compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles, which require that data be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.²⁵ In this way, the value of open data as a public good can still be preserved while fighting inappropriate exploitation and misinterpretation of that data.

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